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TRADE IN THE FOCUS OF FINANCIAL ANALYSIS COMPETITIVENESS OF ENTERPRISES

The article examines the trends in the development of trade and its contribution to the country's economy through the lens of financial analysis of enterprise competitiveness.

Fundamental shifts in the market share structure of trade participants have had a significant impact on this economic sector, competitive processes, and overall economic indicators, highlighting the relevance of the study.

Using the methods of time, structural and trend analysis, the author examines key indicators that characterize the financial situation and efficiency of organizations engaged in trade. The widely used method of comparison and correlation of indicators such as gross added value, net financial result, investments in fixed assets, contributions to the budget system of tax payments, and the number of people employed in the economy, allowed to trace the dynamics of development and directions of change in the field of trade. The analysis is complemented by an assessment of the results of the activities of trade organizations in the Russian Federation, as well as financial indicators such as profitability, asset turnover, liquidity, and solvency.

The article is a valuable source of information for specialists in financial analysis, economics, and management, as well as for practitioners working in the field of trade.

The key findings highlight the importance of trade in the economy and emphasize the need to integrate financial analysis of macroeconomic indicators into the process of assessing the competitiveness of trade enterprises in order to improve the competitiveness of the Russian economy.

Keywords: trade, competition, competitiveness, financial analysis, gross added value, profit, fixed-asset investment, profitability, turnover, liquidity.

- ◆— , %
- , %
- ...▲... , %
- ×- , %
- *— , %

1. 2014-2023 . ([7, 10-11, 12-14]) , -

2023 .. 82,36 % 11176,1 . . 2014 . 20372,58 . .

2016 ., 2019 . 2020 . 96,44 % , 96,13 % 98,61 % .

16,21 % 2014 . 12,81 % 2023 .

2021 12,46 %

2022 13,45 %.

2014 (. 2,3) ,

.2.

2014-2022 .([2])

89,18 % 2014 . 88,81 % 2022 .

.3.

2014-2022 .([2])

230

10,82% 2014 . 11,19% 2022 .

14,18 %-14,79 %, 2015-2017 .

2023 .(.4), 2014 ., 2022 .

2014-2023

.4. 2014-2023 .([8,9])

2024 , 4 2024 .

[5].

2014-2023 . (.5),

.5.

2014-2023 . ([12-14])

2023 ., 2 (40139,97 ., 2014 . 95135,57 137%).

2015-2016 ., 2020-2022 . -

2023

9,7%.

2014

2017, 2020 2022 . 2017 .

232

2020-2022

2014 . 78,7% 2023 . 73,3%
 2014-2023 . 67,0% 71,9%.
 26,7% 21,3% 2023
 (.6).

.6.

2014-2023 .([12-14])

2023 . 120,5%. 79% 554,52 . [1]. 2014 . 1222,8
 2020 .
 3,0-4,0%,
 3,9% 3,6% 1,1 1,9% ()

(.7)

(.7. [10-11]) 2014-2023 ., %

2023 64,7% 2014 71,17% 2023 58,6% 2014 65,31%
2017
2023
5,14% 5,76% 2014 2016 14%,
2014-2023 1%.

.8.

([6, 10-11])

2014-2023 .

2014-2021 .

14,2 % 8,6 %

2021

2021

2014

85,71 %

2020

27,9 %

2023

4,7 %,

.9.

2014-2023 . (

[6, 10-11])

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